

Understanding the Limitations of Single-Event Upset Simulation in Deep Learning Libraries

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Fault Injection (FI) for Single-Event Upset (SEU) simulation is essential to evaluate the reliability of Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) intended for deployment in radiation-intensive environments, such as space. Although accurate FI methods based on Register-Transfer Level (RTL) exist, their computational demands limit scalability. On the other hand, software-based FI simulations are faster but notoriously inaccurate. Moreover, the sources of these inaccuracies are still poorly understood.

This paper contributes to this understanding by performing a comparative analysis of RTL-level FI and DNN-level FI during inference. While the former injects bit-faults at register level in the RTL design of a DNN accelerator, the latter will inject bit-faults in intermediate tensors used by a deep learning library.

Our findings reveal that the DNN-level FI can underestimate critical errors by a factor 3 when compared to the RTL-level FI. The sources of this inaccuracy are identified and opportunities for improving the DNN-level FI are presented.

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is prospected to revolutionise the space industry by facilitating a higher autonomy in spacecrafts, enabling missions that cannot be operated through a conventional ground-in-the-loop operational cycle, due to communication bandwidth and latency constraints. Such a paradigm shift can benefit greatly from AI, and DNNs in particular, to be run on-board of a spacecraft to perform context-aware decisions in real time [1, 2]. As these decisions are potentially safety-critical, the reliability of these DNNs in radiation-intensive environments needs to be assessed to avoid erroneous decisions due to SEUs.

Although physical radiation experiments are suited to characterise the resilience of a final product, SEU simulations are important at earlier stages to steer

hardware and software developments. Many of these simulations include RTL-level FI methods, executed using accurate but slow RTL simulations [3]. On the other hand, FI simulation in high-level deep learning libraries (denoted as DNN-level FI) is faster in terms of execution providing a higher scalability [4], but are also known to be highly inaccurate [5].

While existing literature covers both RTL-level and DNN-level FI for evaluating DNNs, there remains limited understanding regarding the sources of inaccuracies associated with the DNN-level FI. This lack of understanding hinders the development of reliable DNNs for on-board execution.

This paper contributes to this understanding by analysing the inaccuracies based on a comparative experiment between a low RTL-level and a high DNN-level FI methodology. We start with the design of these FI methodologies in Section 2. In Section 3, first the experimental setup is explained, followed by the results and analysis of the comparative study. Finally, in Section 4, we conclude with a discussion on the implications of our findings and propose future research directions.

2 Fault Injection Methodologies

The objective of FI, is to simulate SEUs in a DNN accelerator. The limited energy resources, and capacity for heat dissipation, typically requires the accelerator to be low-power and highly efficient. For this purpose,

Figure 1: Representation of the FI design flow

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Figure 2: RTL architecture for a 2×2 parameterised SA [6] (In this research we use a 8×8 SA, but for brevity a 2×2 SA is shown here.)

this work considers a custom integer-only DNN accelerator based on a 8×8 Systolic Array (SA) designed in [6]. This accelerator can perform quantised DNN inference using 8-bit inputs and weights along with a 32-bit bias. Additionally, its pipeline supports custom activation functions such as Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU).

The process of deploying a DNN on such an accelerator involves several stages. Initially, a DNN model is trained and quantised using a deep learning library. Next, the compilation process generates machine code for model inference which is then deployed on the hardware, or in our scenario on the RTL simulator.

In this flow, there are multiple stages where a FI can be applied. As visualised in Figure 1, this paper compares the DNN-level FI with the RTL-level FI.

2.1 RTL-level Fault Injection

Firstly, we developed a RTL-level FI simulation environment on top of a 8×8 SA based DNN [6]. Figure 2 highlights the architecture of DNN accelerator, showing all registers (using a reg suffix) in which bit-faults can be injected. For reasons of brevity, the figure only shows a 2×2 SA architecture while our simulation uses an 8×8 architecture. As reported in [6], the registers in this figure were divided into eight groups according to their functionality. We will use these groups to facilitate the analysis in the next chapter.

Figure 3: Representation of the DNN-level FI in a quantised layer

2.2 DNN-level Fault Injection

Secondly, we developed a DNN-level FI on top of the PyTorch library. Figure 3 depicts the FI tool applied to a single layer of the DNN. The operation node includes the execution of a specific layer such as a Convolution or Fully-Connected (FC) layer, taking into account weights, biases and inputs to generate an output. The NLF node executes a specific Non Linear Function (NLF).

To simulate the quantisation effects in the accelerator, we designed a Q (Quantise) and DQ (DeQuantise) node at six different positions, as visualised in Figure 3. We use a symmetric quantisation with a power-of-two scaling, based on the methods of Nagel et al. [7]. Since the accelerator uses a 32-bit bias and accumulation, this tool performs a 32-bit quantisation to the bias and the operation output as well. The inputs, weights and NLF are quantised to 8 bits and an 8-bit output quantisation is used to simulate the rounding of the output in the accelerator.

Between these Q and DQ nodes, a node that performs a random FI on the quantised numbers (i.e. integers) is implemented. These six FI nodes are defined as *modules*.

To match the operations of the accelerator in Section 2.1 as close as possible, the design of the *w8*, *i8* and *b32* modules is based on the accelerator properties introduced by He et al. [5]. These include the property that a value stored in a register in the datapath only affects a deterministic set of output neurons.

This is because of the predefined structure in the accelerator architecture. A DNN accelerator usually reuses inputs and parameters to optimise its efficiency, with the consequence that one fault in these registers can affect the value of multiple output neurons of that layer. Because of this, the *w8*, *i8* and *b32* modules are implemented, such that a subset of the layers' output neurons will be affected. Given Formula 1, representing a FC layer where I is the input size and J is the output size, this process takes a subset of the output Y (with $y_j \in Y$), as explained in Algorithm 1.

$$y_j = b_j + \sum_{i=0}^{I-1} x_i w_{ij} \text{ with } j \in [1, J - 1] \quad (1)$$

Algorithm 1 FI subsetting

1. Compute **golden output** neurons (without FI).
2. Compute **faulty outputs** by flipping a randomly selected bit across all modules positioned before the operation node, such that every output that uses this value is faulty.
3. Take the golden output and replace a **subset** S (determined by Formula 2) with the corresponding faulty output.

$$S = \left[j, \left(\left\lfloor \frac{j}{8} \right\rfloor + 1 \right) \cdot 8 \right] \text{ with } j \in [0, J - 1] \quad (2)$$

Because faults in the *o32*, *o8* and *nlf8* modules only affect the value of one output neuron, these modules are simply implemented as a random FI.

3 Experiments and Analysis

3.1 Experiment setup

In order to better understand the differences between the two FI methodologies, we conducted an experiment that uses two simple models trained on the MNIST dataset using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of $2e-3$ and a batch size of 32. Both models have an input size of 784 and 10 output classes:

- **FC** (One FC Layer), trained for 1 epoch.
- **Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)** (three FC layers), which uses a ReLU NLF and has 100 and 50 output neurons in the first and second layer respectively. This network was trained for 5 epochs.

For both models we perform 1000 inferences for each of 100 randomly chosen MNIST images. Each inference, we flip a randomly selected bit across all registers or modules respectively for both FI methods.

Table 1: Distribution of register groups and modules in generic collections

Generic	RTL FI regs	legend	DNN FI	legend
input	sa-ffchain-h			
	sa-h			
weight	w			
p/out32	sa-v			
	sa-ffchain-v			
	accum			
out8	round			
nlf	nlf			

Additionally, to make a meaningful comparison between the two FI methods, we compared them from two distinct perspectives. Firstly, we determined the probability that each method introduces a bit-fault within a certain collection, which is defined as the **Injection Probability** (P_I). Secondly, we analysed the consequences of such a bit-fault for both methods using two different metrics:

- **Logit Fault Probability** (P_{LF}): The probability that a bit-fault is injected in a certain collection and causes a difference at the output logits.
- **False Classification Probability** (P_{FC}): The probability that a bit-fault is injected in a certain collection and causes a different classification compared to the original (or golden) classification.

3.2 Result

This section presents a comparative analysis of the experiment results. Since the RTL-level FI injects at register level and the DNN-level FI injects in modules, these two methods are not directly equivalent. Therefore we divide the register groups from the RTL-level experiment and the modules from the DNN-level experiment into generic collections that can be compared. The distribution of these collections is visualised in Table 1.

Figure 4 shows the results of the previously discussed metrics. The left-hand side features three plots with the metrics applied on the FC model, while the right-hand side shows the metrics applied to the MLP model. The legend of the bars in this figure is provided in Table 1.

Initially, we observe a significant disparity between the P_I of the two methods. Specifically, the DNN-level FI method predominantly injects faults in the weight modules, whereas the RTL-level FI methodology primarily targets the 32-bit register groups. A more thorough analysis of this disparity is performed in Section 3.3.

Figure 4: P_I , P_{LF} and P_{FC} for the FC and MLP networks

The P_{LF} plots show a similar distribution mismatch between the two injection methods across the different collections. However, compared to the P_I plots, it is remarkable that the RTL-level probability values shrink relatively to the DNN-level FI. This implies that given an injection in any of the collections, the likelihood of observing a logit fault is significantly smaller for the RTL-level FI method. This observation is due to the fact that in the RTL-level method, not every register where a fault is injected is also actively used in that clock cycle. Some registers are idle during the operation of the accelerator and are thus not vulnerable to faults at that moment. By contrast, in the DNN-level FI method, every module is always active and thus continually vulnerable to faults.

In the P_{FC} plots, one can observe that the 32-bit collection has the highest probability in both FI methodologies. In fact, the share of this collection is significantly larger than in the previous metrics. This observation aligns with the findings of Li et al. [8], where the authors concluded that the impact of faults in numbers with a high Dynamic Range (DR) is larger than with a low DR. In this case, this means that 32-bit registers, who have a high DR, have a higher P_{FC} than the 8-bit registers.

Finally, the overall P_{FC} of the RTL-level FI method is more than 3x higher than the DNN-level FI method. This is due to the fact that the RTL-level FI method injects more faults in the 32-bit collections, which have a higher probability of causing a false classification. This underestimation of the DNN-level FI shows a great risk of underestimating the reliability of the DNN in a radiation environment.

3.3 Opportunities for improvement

The most interesting observation from the previous section is the large disparity between the P_I metric of the two FI methodologies. Given the foundational role of this metric in the design of a FI method, this section presents an analysis of the cause of this disparity.

Section 2.1 explained that every bit in every register and clock cycle has the same probability to receive a fault. In the same way, section 2.2 explained that every bit in every module has the same probability to receive a fault. However, there is a different behaviour between the FI in registers and in modules. Using formula 1, it is possible to determine two reasons for this different behaviour in a FC layer:

- **Reuse of inputs:** A single input element x_i is used in the calculation of every output y_j because of its usage in J partial multiplications $x_i w_{ij}$. This means that the same input has to be stored in an input register for J times. As a result, the P_I of inputs in the RTL-level simulation increases.
- **Partial Sums (psums):** The calculation of an output y_j takes the sum of every partial multiplication $x_i \cdot w_{ij}$. Therefore, to calculate an output at least I psums have to be stored in a *p/out32* register. This increases the P_I of this collection.

Note that in a FC layer, weights and biases are not reused. However in other layers this might be the case.

These reasons highlight that the P_I of the input and the 32-bit collections are significantly underestimated in the DNN-level FI method. However, the amount of psums and reuse of inputs is deterministic and only depends on the layer size and the DNN accelerator architecture. Therefore, it is possible to correctly adjust the P_I of the modules in the DNN-level FI method to better match the RTL-level FI method.

4 Conclusion

This research provides a comparative analysis between a low RTL-level and a high DNN-level FI methodology. The study has identified that the DNN-level FI underestimates the False Classification Probability by a factor 3, meaning that one also underestimates the reliability of DNNs in harsh radiation environments. However, the study also provides a promising direction for future research. The deterministic nature of the data path in a DNN accelerator suggests that it is possible to adjust the DNN-level FI to better match the RTL-level FI method. This paves the way to more accurate and scalable SEU simulations.

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